

Effectiveness of health education regarding importance of early initiation of breastfeeding among antenatal mothers at civil hospital hoshiarpur, punjab

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Abstract:

Early initiation of breastfeeding defined as putting the newborn to the breast within one hour of birth, is a critical public health practice that significantly reduces neonatal morbidity and mortality. Breast milk particularly colostrum provides essential nutrients and antibodies that protect newborns against infection and promote growth and development. Despite strong recommendations from the World Health Organization and UNICEF, the practice of early initiation of breastfeeding remains suboptimal in many developing countries including India. Factors such as inadequate antenatal counselling, limited awareness, cultural beliefs, misconceptions, fear of pain and influence of family members often delay the initiation of breastfeeding. **Methodology:** A Quantitative Research Approach and Pre-Experimental (one-group pre-test and post-test) research design was adopted to assess the effectiveness of Health Education regarding the importance of early initiation of breastfeeding on the knowledge among antenatal mothers. The study was conducted in selected Civil Hospital, Hoshiarpur, Punjab. A sample of total 40 antenatal mothers was selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. **Results:** Results depicted that mean pre-test knowledge score was 14.9 ± 2.25 and mean post-test knowledge score was 24.9 ± 2.07 . The findings of the study revealed that the difference in mean scores was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ level. This indicates that the health education program was effective in improving knowledge regarding the early initiation of breastfeeding. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that health education is an effective strategy in enhancing the knowledge of antenatal mothers regarding the importance of early initiation of breastfeeding. Improved maternal knowledge can contribute to better breastfeeding practices and positive neonatal health outcomes.

Keywords:

Breastfeeding, Newborn, Morbidity, WHO, UNICEF, Health education, Antenatal mothers etc.
